

ReBioCycle Pulse

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Feature 4/2025 – Sorting bioplastics at scale in Turin, JRC survey on recycling, enzymatic recycling, and upcoming Bioplastics Recycling Cluster talks

ReBioCycle

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1- The Circular Plastic Plant of Amiat: Sorting bioplastics at scale

AMIAT | Gruppo Iren is the company that, for over fifty years, has been committed to making Turin an increasingly liveable, clean, and sustainable city. Amiat is a partner in ReBioCycle: Amiat manages soil hygiene, waste collection, and disposal services in an integrated manner, with a circular perspective of recovery and valorisation. In the daily management of services, as in future planning, Amiat adopts the principles of circular

economy and ecology, responding proactively and effectively to the challenges of protecting the territory and public health.

Amiat collects 450.000 tons of waste per year, serving 1.1 million inhabitants through 19 collection sites and five plants. The company operates a separate urban waste collection throughout the city of Turin in two different modes: Street Separate Collection and Home Separate Collection. This is divided into Porta A Porta and Eco-island modes. In 2024, the data for the waste collection in Turin were as follows:

Waste collection (TURIN 2024)	Amount (tons/year)
Municipal solid waste/solid urban waste (with road sweeping)	190.000
Organic	52.000
Paper	45.000
Wood	20.000
Plastic	22.000
Glass and metal	32.000
Other separately collected waste:	20.000 (total):
• bulks	• 6.700
• aggregates	• 3.600
• WEEE	• 2.200
• textile	• 2.000

In all cases, the residual bioplastic content in the separated collected waste streams was limited and manageable. In the case of "plastic" and "organic" streams, bioplastic materials were present at a concentration below 2%, while they were present in trace amounts in the case of paper, glass and metals separately collected, and not present in the case of wood and other separately collected waste (bulky, aggregates, WEEE, textile...).

Innovating the collection: improving the quality of collected waste: Over the past year, Amiat has implemented various strategies to enhance the quality of selected waste and is currently conducting trials with image recognition technology to gather data on the types of waste in bins, their fill levels, and the quality of sorted materials. Additionally, Amiat has identified instances of improper waste disposal in the vicinity of dumpsters. The next step for Amiat was to use the information to refine the best collection patch by processing data collected for each user to reschedule collection routes, and to assess the evolution over time of the quality of Separate Waste Collection.

Amiat, I.BLU sorting plant at Borgaro Torinese: The Circular Plastic Plant: The plant occupies circa 76.000 square meters and has an area of circa 20.000 square meters. It is in the north of Turin, in Borgaro Torinese. The plant uses the following technologies: 1 bag opener machine, 2 rotary screens, 4 ballistic screens, 22 optical readers, 124 conveyor belts, and 2 baling presses. It can process 100.000 tons/year (authorised processing capacity), with a maximum selection rate of 17 tons/hour, 2.430 tons of input plastic storage, and 11.210 tons of output plastic storage. There are still employees at the plant working to support sorting the waste.

Currently, Amiat, in collaboration with Iren's Innovation Directorate, is testing advanced technologies and software to support operators responsible for the qualitative assessment of materials downstream of the automatic cleaning and sorting systems. These solutions aim to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of quality checks following the automated processing stage.

Fig. 1: Technologies used at the Circular Plastic Plant. Source: Amiat.

Within ReBioCycle, the input waste from the Circular Plastic Plant has been assessed to verify polymer compositions and quantifications, and to give special attention to the biodegradable plastic content through scheduled analyses of plastic waste. 2.000 tons of input waste have been processed during these tests, resulting in a quantification of the content of bioplastics at $0,51\% \pm 0,19\%$.

From April to September 2025, the ReBioCycle partners **Gruppo Iren** and **Novamont** collaborated at the plant to develop a Near Infrared (NIR) database to identify rigid and flexible bioplastics in real-world plastic waste. The activity has been using virgin bioplastic items by leveraging a pre-loaded bioplastic recognition software and integrating it with different types of spectra obtained from virgin bioplastic specimens and real bioplastic items recovered manually from the plastic waste stream. The first full-scale NIR sorting activity was successfully performed.

The following tests were performed with actual plant runs, testing its capacity to select bioplastics and creating a dataset on input quantity and bioplastics output. The bioplastic sample was efficiently selected at the full-scale level, while materials different from bioplastics were removed and quantified.

Fig. 2: From identification of rigid and flexible plastics to sorting. The bioplastic sample was positively selected at the full-scale level. Source: Amiat.

Video: The bioplastic conveyor belt at the Circular Plastic Plant, Turin (IT). Source: Amiat, edits by European Bioplastics.

2- Joint Research Centre survey on mechanical, physical, and chemical recycling technologies at TRL9 for plastic packaging.

The Joint Research Centre has launched a survey on mechanical, physical, and chemical recycling technologies for plastic packaging.

The JRC is supporting the **Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (EU 2025/40)**, and more specifically, the development of implementing acts under its Article 7, by assessing the economic and environmental performance of plastic packaging recycling technologies. Your input will help build a comprehensive data inventory that will inform policymaking." For each plastic packaging category, they are collecting data on:

- ✓ Input/output quantities & characteristics
- ✓ Resources used
- ✓ Costs & revenues

The JRC is looking for data from operational industrial recycling installations (TRL 9). Deadline to reply to the survey is 12 January 2026.

To access the survey, visit this LinkedIn post: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7394367043099303936/>

This type of contribution is key to bringing bioplastics recycling to the fore at its current state of play, so that the policy door is not closed to them.

JRC
**Plastic
Recyclers
Survey**

Send your contribution to support the Recycling Sustainability Assessment under the PPWR

3- Enzymatic recycling of PHA in ReBioCycle: A chat with Laura de Eugenio (CSIC)

A new publication by Laura de Eugenio and colleagues is available on New Biotechnology, in open access. Our research in ReBioCycle has aimed to explore the possibilities of enzymatic recycling of PHA under conditions that resemble practical applications. We worked with enzymes obtained through heterologous expression systems and applied them without purification to keep the process closer to scalable production schemes. The material was examined in both its original form and after pretreatments that alter its structure and surface properties, allowing us to see how such changes affect its interaction with enzymes. Throughout the work, we followed the generation of soluble products as a simple indicator of progress in depolymerisation. Rather than focusing on maximising individual parameters, the intention was to understand how the different elements, such as enzyme preparation, polymer conditioning, and product recovery, fit together in a single process. This provides a first step toward evaluating feasibility, while also highlighting aspects that will require longer-term innovation before the approach can be translated into larger-scale practice.

Resources: José D. Jiménez, Manuel S. Godoy, Carlos del Cerro, M. Auxiliadora Prieto, Hints from nature for a PHA circular economy: Carbon synthesis and sharing by *Pseudomonas solani* GK13, New Biotechnology, Volume 84, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2024.09.002>.

About Laura de Eugenio: Laura de Eugenio is a senior researcher at the Center for Biological Research (CIB). CIB is one of the most prestigious and historical research centers of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). Laura's profile is on [Google Scholar](#). Find out more about Laura's and CIB's role in ReBioCycle: [a 3- minute interview](#).

4- Bioplastics Recycling Cluster talks in 2026: PLA sorting, microbial recycling and highlights on emerging certification schemes for recycling

Are you an expert in recycling of bioplastics, or sorting or collecting? Are you working on this topic and would like to exchange with peers?

Look no further, this series of talks is for you! Join our community of experts, we have three exciting upcoming talks in January, February and March:

Tuesday 13 January 2026: PLA sorting model Speaker: Wang Li, Univ. Ghent, PROSPER

Tuesday 3 February 2026: Microbial recycling for bioplastics Speaker: Joao Sousa, Paques Biomaterials, ReBioCycle

Tuesday 3 March 2026: The certification scheme OK Recycled certification and labelling Speaker: Giulia Finazzi, TÜV Austria Italy – ReBioCycle and MoeBIOS advisor

Registration on this page: <https://www.eventbrite.com/cc/bioplastics-recycling-cluster-talks-4428313>

The series started in September 2025 and continues until March 2026.

A second edition will resume in September 2026 with a new calendar of talks!

[Registration on this page](#)

Sulapac on Design for Recycling at the Bioplastics Recycling Cluster talk in November

[Laura Tirkkonen-Rajasalo](#), of [Sulapac Ltd](#), shared her experience advocating with the Council, the European Commission, and the Parliament in the journey to include biodegradable plastics in the [PPWR](#).

About Sulapac becoming recyclable <https://zenodo.org/records/17529015>

Presentation on Design for Recycling criteria for bioplastics packaging, a presentation by [European Bioplastics](#) <https://zenodo.org/records/17524013>

Recording of the session: <https://youtu.be/INoTj-7plfs>

Bioplastics Recycling Cluster Talks

Design for Recycling criteria for bioplastics packaging

4 November, 2025
online

Lorette Du Preez, European Bioplastics
Laura Tirkkonen-Rajasalo, SULAPAC

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